

In this document you can find the questions that were asked to the students at the end of the trial period presented in the associated report, Use of OneNote as an ELN in undergraduate teaching labs at the University of Southampton in the department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering. Answers to some of these questions, using the supplementary data provided, were used to generate a number of the images in the report. Question 1 has had the data removed from the supplementary data to make the data anonymous.

Questions

Q0. PIS and consent form

Q1. Please insert the unique identifier that you have created here – Removed from Results Data

Q2. Do you currently make electronic links between any academic notes you write and any digital files or data outputs that you create? **(yes/no question)**

Q3. What qualities/elements do you think make good notes? **(short text answer)**

Q4. What do you think is poor/bad practice when taking notes? **(short text answer)**

Q5. When organising your digital academic work do you organise it in a specific way? **(yes/no question)**

Q6. Has the way in which you organise your digital academic work changed since the beginning of this module? **(yes/no question)**

Q7. If you answered yes to Q6, could you briefly describe how you do this? **(short text answer)**

Q8. Please rank what you believe are the most important to least important capabilities of digital note taking? **(list to be ordered)**

- Ability to take and access note anywhere (with an internet connection)
- Ability to add images/photos to a set of notes
- Ability to incorporate mathematical notation
- Ability to incorporate drawings such as chemical structure or diagrams
- Ability to directly link your notes to other notes/data files
- Ability to type out notes rather than writing by hand
- Ability to go back and find the notes you are looking for easily
- Ability to make free form notes wherever you want on the page

Q9. Did you use any form of electronic note taking prior to October 2024? **(yes/no question)**

Q10. What was the best feature from the OneNote lab book? **(short text answer)**

Q11. What was missing from the OneNote lab book? **(short text answer)**

Q12. How useful was the outline lab page? **(Likert scale from not useful to very useful)**

Q13. Did you ever add anything to the document that wasn't suggested in the outline? **(Likert scale from never to lots)**

Q14. After this experience would you use OneNote (or another digital note taking software) to take notes in classes/personal use were they were not prescribed? **(Likert scale from unlikely to likely)**

Q15. Having experienced using digital note taking would you go back to paper note taking, and if yes why and where? **(short text question)**

Q16. Do you think your lab notes are better at the end of the module than they were at the beginning? **(yes/no)**

Q17. If you answered yes to question Q16, how much do you think your note taking has improved **(Likert Scale from minimal to a lot, probably with an N/A option for those that said no)**

Q18. How did you add specific chemical notations to your work? **(multiple choice, multiple answers allowed)**

- Drew on paper and inserted photos
- Used ChemDraw or similar such tool
- Inbuilt symbols and equations functionality
- SMILES or similar inline notation
- Written words

Q19. Did the lack of chemical tool integration with OneNote cause you problems? **(yes/no question)**

Q20. If you answered yes to Q20, could you briefly explain why? **(short answer text)**

Q21. Would integration of chemical tools improve the note taking experience? **(yes/no)**

Q22. How easy did you find it to search for something in your notes? **(Likert scale)**

Q23. How easy did you find it to understand your previous notes in this module compared to handwritten notes? **(Likert scale from difficult to easy)**

Q24. Do you think you would be able to revise for an exam using these notes? **(yes/no question)**

Q25. Any other comments on this module's use of OneNote as a lab book? **(short text answer)**